
**THE POETIC REPRESENTATION OF CITY AND URBAN DWELLERS'
LIFE IN THE STORIES OF SHUKUR XOLMIRZAYEV**

Mohichehra O‘rolova

Termiz State University, 3rd year student

mohichehraulova@gmail.com

Academic Supervisor: **Normat Yo‘ldoshev**

Annotation: This article explores the stories of Shukur Xolmirzayev, focusing on the depiction of urban environments and the people who inhabit them. It examines the unique lifestyle of city dwellers and characterizes them in a poetic manner.

Keywords: Storytelling, story, writer, literature, genre, character, depiction of city and urban dwellers, person, characteristics, life, character.

Shukur Xolmirzayev, who came to the Uzbek literary process in the 1960s with his early works, caught the attention of the mentor Abdulla Qahhor. While he created various examples in many genres throughout his literary career, his activities in storytelling stand out. Being well-informed about world literature, he expanded the possibilities of the storytelling genre even further after Abdulla Qahhor. In this regard, the writer himself considers Abdulla Qahhor as his mentor and expresses the following thoughts: "I do not lack Abdulla Qahhor, that is, not coming to life, stories, 'Sarob' – our imagination, I closed my eyes. The world became dark. I... ceased to exist. If I open my eyes, he's in front of me. So I'm alive too."

In his stories, Shukur Xolmirzayev primarily strives to portray four types of characters.

1. City Dwellers
2. Village Dwellers
3. Desert Dwellers
4. Mountain Dwellers

These types of characters depict them in harmony with nature. They vividly portray the relationship between humans and nature in profound ways through their works. By condensing their content, they convey several meanings. It encourages readers to contemplate and draw their own conclusions independently. In this regard, literary scholar Qozoqboy Yo‘ldosh stated: "Extracting the student's soul from conformity, not allowing it to fall into a situation where it does not engage in artistic imagery, is the victory of any writer."

Teacher Abdulla Qahhor wrote: "A writer often writes when inspiration strikes, and hesitates to put pen to paper when it does not. But it is clear that when inspiration comes, the writer understands it fully, and when it does not, the writer still does not

grasp it." Like emphasized by the teacher, Shukur Xolmirzayev is a complete creator. He writes every word in his works with feeling. Because as the writer himself emphasizes, he revises each work multiple times before submitting it for publication; if he does not feel satisfied with anything, he does not publish it. The writer's works are still beloved because they were written with inspiration and feeling.

In Shukur Xolmirzayev's stories, the depicted characters never repeat themselves. Each time, he uncovers new events and characters, thereby revealing their internal characteristics. Shukur Xolmirzayev is a writer who opens up emotional feelings. His stories such as "Something Was Missing", "The Law of Abandoning the World", "An Empty Yard", and "Teacher" prove our earlier conclusions. In the story "The Law of Abandoning the World", the writer tells the story of a simple person named Husan who lives humbly within the confines of the city. Most people imagine city dwellers as arrogant, proud, and insatiable. However, those who read this story come away with a different understanding.

Because the protagonist of the story, Husan aka, was a sincere person who greeted everyone from the elderly to the young with a simple "you", even addressing his daughters with "you". Just like how people are not perfect, Husan aka also had one weakness. When he saw someone of a higher status, he would tremble and stutter, as if that person were determining his fate in that moment. After Husan aka had six daughters, he finally had a son. For his son, he called several officials, hugged them, and gave gifts. This pattern repeated several times on his son's birthday. Then one day, his son suddenly died. Well-known guests came to the funeral. Husan aka never complained about the death of his son, he stared at his family members and the guests in the eye and gave his son a farewell. It can be seen that during Husan aka's final moments, his family and son, as well as high-ranking individuals and accolades, were precious to him, and he understood the value of his feelings. The writer, however, appears to be attempting to reprimand anyone who resembles Husan aka by taking lessons from his destiny.

In the story "Teacher," the writer seeks to portray the character through their actions, movements, and speech. In the story, everything needed by the teacher is there: cars, villas, and books, which are still in circulation, all of which have been obtained. However, with a sense of doubt, the desire to be a means of a disciple's death. He turned out to be a person who gave help to a disciple, but actually, he turned into an longed one his. However, this time Qismatilla did not take the lead, and they continued in this situation for quite some time. Consequently, their relationship gradually deteriorated due to lack of affection, happiness, and luck.

In his story "An Empty Yard," Shukur Xolmirzayev brilliantly opens the issue of blindness. In the story, Umar aka and his daughter-in-law Hosila send their son Ummat to the army. Since Ummat was their only child, they cherished him greatly,

considering all the luxuries they acquired from a major store to be for him. After settling down, they stocked their current store with various goods and kept the profits in their chests. They adorned the walls of their home after their son left and painted over the walls. When their son left, his beloved dog also passed away, and they replaced it with another dog of the same breed. They presented themselves as simple to the villagers in the village, but sometimes deceived customers, took their money, and came home, claiming to have done their work. One evening, when their son returned from the army and found the door locked without anyone opening it, he jumped over the fence to surprise them, and the dog amazed him. In this way, they accumulated ill-gotten gains, not sharing them with their only son due to their blindness, ultimately receiving a deserved punishment for their deeds.

In conclusion, it is clear that in the stories analyzed above, we see unique lifestyles and characteristics specific to urban dwellers. The writer skillfully portrays topics and issues unique to urban environments in a realistic and genuine manner, molding the characters with distinctive traits. Furthermore, the writer does not merely narrate the lives of these characters in these stories; rather, he skillfully depicts the social environment and conditions with expertise.

References:

1. Shukur Xolmirzayev. "I Consider Literature My Destiny...: Literary Thoughts, Articles, Conversations." Tashkent: "Sharq", 2022. Pages 126-127.
2. Qozoqboy Yo'ldosh. "Bright Words." Tashkent: "Yangi Asr Avlodi", 2006. Page 354.
3. Abdulla Qahhor. "The Power of Truthful Words: Articles and Conversations." Rules. Tashkent: Adabiyot va San'at Nashriyoti, 1989. Page 66.
4. <https://www.ziyouz.com>